

Spontaneous Behavior Relationship Management by Speed of Information Flow

Dr. Nasser Fegh-hi Farahmand¹, Shirin Pour Haji Ali Farid²

¹Department of Management, Tabriz Branch, Islamic Azad University, Tabriz, Iran.

²East Azerbaijan Behzisti Organization, Tabriz, Iran.

Abstract

The strategy implementation, strategic control, spontaneous behavior and successful measurement literature develop a conceptual model and research propositions. In fact, without organizational customers organizations would not exist. The strategic importance of organizational customers is discussed as an asset. Also this paper describes the approach to organizational relationship management at organizations. This paper proposes a relation of organizational relationship management by speed of information flow and reviews the spontaneous behavior strategies and performance measurement literature to develop a conceptual model and research propositions. In fact, organizations influence whether or not those organizations engage in spontaneous behavior strategies. In this field, the focus is on the special characteristics of speed of information flow such as education type and level. The facilitator manager's characteristics showing a significant association with a commitment to organizational relationship management and also organizational relationship management showed a positive association with those speed of information flow with a growth orientation. It is concluded that facilitator manager's characteristics can be important in explaining and compilation the organizational relationship management within the organizations for implementation. This paper is to explore the ways in which certain characteristics of speed of information flow of organizations generate a tendency to prepare formal written spontaneous behavior strategies.

Keywords: Organizational Relationship Management; Speed of Information Flow; Spontaneous Behavior Strategies; Spontaneous Behavior Relationship Management.

1. Introduction

A positive experience throughout the customer's cycle should foster trust and develop loyalty, therefore allowing organizations to generate more revenue for less incremental expenditure as:

- I. Making new customers aware of a product or service with loyal customers tend to receive more frequently and happy existing customers are more willing to receive other services from organization and try new service offerings.

- II. The cost of servicing existing customers can be lower by security of future revenues, which is much higher with happy customers.

For strategic purposes, satisfy of an intangible asset in its own right is not particularly relevant; however, an understanding of how this satisfy is comprised and the key metrics that impact on the assets' contribution to organization successful can be extremely beneficial for management decision making. Recent research into strategy implementation is damning in its findings. The organizations field is now giving high priority to developing metrics.

The role of organizations is to implement strategy. A fundamental proposition in strategy is that distribution methods must be aligned with customers and competitive advantage. Unfortunately, method successful measurement literature has provided ambiguous guidance to managers.

In order to achieve spontaneous behavior success, it is important to understand the relationship between method successful measures and strategy implementation success. It is also important to know whether, regardless of strategy, the same method successful measures should be used.

The key question in terms of ensuring that method strategy supports spontaneous behavior successful is how do we know our method strategy is performing? In order to understand whether the method is performing or not, we need to ensure that the method measures are appropriate for each spontaneous behavior strategy. Although organizational relationship management has been one of the fastest growing organizations, critics point to the high failure rate of the organizational relationship management projects as evidenced by organizations studies. The purpose of the study is to investigate success and failures of organizational relationship management system implementations. Also this study found that the scope, size, complexity and duration of the organizational relationship management projects seem to vary quite significantly across organizations. Poor planning, lack of clear objectives and not recognizing the need for organization change are the key reasons for organizational relationship management failures. The spontaneous behavior field is now giving high priority to developing spontaneous behavior metrics. The role of spontaneous behavior is to implement spontaneous behavior strategy. Effective organizational relationship management is one of the important factors in organizations success. There is speed of information flow who argue that formal written planning may be inappropriate for the organizations but this seems a minority view. It can be argued that organizational relationship management is as important to organizations as to larger organizations and standard textbooks on entrepreneurship offer chapters on spontaneous behavior plan whilst a range of specialist publications outline the best ways of writing spontaneous behavior plan (Sahlman, 1997, 67; Monks, 2001, 41; Naffziger, et al, 1991, 21). A fundamental proposition in spontaneous behavior strategy is that spontaneous behavior plan must be aligned with customers and competitive advantage.

Unfortunately, spontaneous behavior plan performance measurement literature has provided ambiguous guidance to spontaneous behavior managers. In organizations, where a spontaneous behavior strategy exists, the preparation of the organizational relationship management may have been driven by external forces. The most obvious of these are the requirements of external agencies providing funding for either start up or expansion. However, the spontaneous behavior strategies may serve as a strategic planning document for the managers, entrepreneurs and educated workers, a plan to guide the spontaneous behavior and serve as a basis for taking strategic decisions and also it may serve as a subsequent monitoring device (Deakins, 2003, 329; Feghhi farahmand, 2005, 118). In view of its perceived ongoing value to the small business it might be expected that organizational relationship management would be a feature of many, if not most, organizations. In order to achieve spontaneous behavior success, it is important to understand the relationship between Organizational relationship management by Educated Managers and strategy deployment success. As management itself becomes more emphatically fast-paced and intuitive, in order to deal with complexity and unpredictability, research is beginning to accumulate showing that coaching formats used in management support are

more effective than training in the older logical comprehensive pursuits.

2. Spontaneous Behavior Strategies

The spontaneous behavior relationship model suggests strategy is a more important influence on method measures than variables such as spontaneous behavior relationship characteristics, stage of service lifecycle, market share, organizational or strategic organization unit size, profitability and growth, environment or competitors. Table 1 shows the proposed relationships between method measures for each strategy type.

Table 1: Organizations Strategy Types

No	New Guidelines Strategy	Old Guidelines Strategy
1	Spontaneous behavior pull	Spontaneous behavior Push
2	Frequent spontaneous behavior	Infrequent spontaneous behavior
3	Social spontaneous behavior	Economic spontaneous behavior
4	Spontaneous behavior quality / qualitative	Spontaneous behavior cost / quantitative
5	Environmental spontaneous behavior	Organizational spontaneous behavior
6	Strategically / Long-term spontaneous behavior	Operational / Short-term spontaneous behavior

Strategy 1- Spontaneous Behavior Pull Vs Spontaneous Behavior Push: Traditional successful measurement systems were profitable focused and were neither multidimensional nor strategic. Based on the degree of service innovation inherent in strategies, it is likely that they would compete with higher quality services and be first to market with new generation services. Conversely, pull strategy would depend more on efficiency and cost reduction to compete and rely more on older generation services. As a result, pull would place greater emphasis on cost control measures in supporting strategy. pull measures of managers may be more important than pull measures of successful.

Strategy 2- Frequent Spontaneous Behavior Vs Infrequent Spontaneous Behavior: Control by successful large pull involved frequent successful reporting. Pull spontaneous behavior would be expected to be similar to cost leaders as they operate in relatively certain environments with existing service receivers and undertake little service innovation. As a result, the measures they use could be frequent yet still be meaningful.

Strategy 3- Social Spontaneous Behavior Vs Economic Spontaneous Behavior: spontaneous behavior relationship management were outcome focused and neither multidimensional nor strategic. The control method of successful pull included careful output monitoring and was expected to be associated with pull.

Strategy 4- Spontaneous Behavior Quality / Qualitative Vs Spontaneous Behavior Cost / Quantitative: Based on the degree of service innovation inherent in pull strategies, it is likely that they would compete with higher quality services and be first to market with new generation services. Conversely, pull would depend more on efficiency and cost reduction to compete and rely more on older generation services. As a result, pull would place greater emphasis on cost control measures in supporting organizations strategy.

Strategy 5- Environmental Spontaneous Behavior Vs Organizational Spontaneous Behavior: As pull target new markets, it appears appropriate they emphasis environmental measures. Conversely, pull would rely more on organizational and need to monitor internal efficiency while they compete with older generation services.

Strategy 6- Strategically Spontaneous Behavior Vs Operational Spontaneous Behavior: Successful measures must be aligned with organization strategy. The optimum control system required two different approaches operating at different hierarchal levels.

The literature argues shows that the extent to which each determinant of performance impacts firm performance is a function of the performance metrics. Further, define performance as the sum of all processes that will lead managers to taking appropriate actions in the present that will create a performing organization in the future or in other words, doing today what will lead to measured value outcomes tomorrow. Speed of information flow' recent research reviewing corporate coaching programs that we can see this move from intuition towards rationalized models as complementary and off-setting to developments in strategic management (Mintzberg, 1994, 89; Mintzberg, et al, 1998, 45; Schwenk, et al, 1993, 17). Like all scientific enterprises, a period of accumulation of evidence will be required before definitive conclusions may be drawn (Brown, et al, 1998, 88; Deakin, et al 2003, 64; Mason, et al, 2004, 3). However, there are early gleanings that evidence based evaluation research is underway. For this reason by coupling quality with customer service recovering satisfaction as Figure 1, a few tactical actions for implementation (Mason and Stark, 2004, 205; Peters, 1988, 160) can make the challenge simpler and provide leadership (Minnow, 1996, 5; Feghhi farahmand, 2009; Rue & et al, 1998, 97).

Figure 1: Spontaneous Behavior Strategies Model

Creative spontaneous behavior building is found in knowledge-based industries, which span many sectors finance, technology, media and learning. Central to success as knowledge creators is the culturing of independent individuals, organizational members able to re-invent businesses as required. Such capabilities are not nurtured in high compliance systems that penalize out-of-envelope contributions (Goleman, 1996, 89; Goleman, et al, 2002, 185; Hamel, 2001, 89; Feghhi farahmand, 2003, 67). Any how spontaneous behavior strategies search few question such as:

- I. How does spontaneous behavior affect customer value?
- II. How strategic planning is carried out at different levels of the organization?
- III. What does a spontaneous behavior plan include?

For this reason Spontaneous behavior & Customer Value and the Value Delivery Process is as follow:

Choosing (or Identifying) + Providing (or Delivering) + Communicating Superior Value

To assist in understanding the process used in a certain application; avoid potential misconceptions regarding the intent and define the activities associated with specific value studies, reclamation has defined four distinct types of value studies.

Also the value chain is a tool to identify key activities that create value & costs in spontaneous behavior and identify ways to create more customer value. Therefore organizational capability relies in particular on coaching management skills, which rely on emotional intelligence and emphasis one-to-one, dialoguing, subordinate empowerment and mutually agreed targeting.

In relation of value core competencies including outsource less critical resources if better quality or cost and own competencies - core business, three characteristics are competitive advantage, applications - many markets and difficult to imitate. For this reason three key questions as value exploration for new opportunities, value creation for new offerings and value delivery for deliver more efficiently is necessary in according

Anyhow tactical actions steps for coupling quality with customers or customers including three Vs to Spontaneous behavior: Value segment, Value proposition, and Value network recovering satisfaction are as follows (Curran, et al, 1994; Feghhi farahmand, 2004, 358; Feghhi farahmand, 2005, 187; Nayak, et al, 1994, 47; North, et al, 1997, 187):

- I. Top manager support: An organization's total quality efforts must begin at the very top and begin with the board of directors (Olivero, et al, 1997, 68; Senge, 1990, 196; Perry, 2001, 66).
- II. Action plan: An action plan based on the survey feedback should then be formulated by the top management and communicated at every board meeting.
- III. Vision: Develop a vision the organization does not have one already. The key to the initial adoption of quality is continuous communication of the vision within a comprehensive communication plan.
- IV. Quality improvements: Senior managers need coaching as the new theorists in coaching argue; coaching empowers individuals to achieve their inherent potential.
- V. Quality circles: Employees, shareholders and customers, suppliers and competitors have a stake and essential ingredient for success is senior quality circles, which provides leadership in quality and stimulates cultural change.
- VI. Responsibility: The responsibilities accept of a senior quality committee can include (Feghhi farahmand, 2004, 398): establishing strategic quality goals, allocating resources, sanctioning quality improvement teams, reviewing key indicators of quality, estimating the cost of poor quality, ensuring adequate training of employees and recognizing and rewarding individual and team efforts.
- VII. Satisfaction: This survey should be sponsored by the top management to send a clear message throughout the organization that quality is linked to customer satisfaction and the senior executives should then present the results to all employees that detailed strategies for improving customer satisfaction can be devised and communicated.

In hypercompetitive economy more rational buyers many choices, company win by fine tuning value delivery process & to choose, provide and communicate superior value. To ensure the opportunity to achieve the highest value, value program staff attempt to keep management or administration directed mission charges flexible enough to allow innovation. This staff make most of the recommendations for administrative and procurement processes that could

benefit from studies (Feghhi farahmand, 2009, 97; Steele, 1997, 28-68; Storey, 1994, 55; Storey & et al, 1989, 97). Anyhow is the need to develop a means to inform administrative or procurement staff of the available resources and how to obtain assistance. Therefore core product or service quality and customer benefits return as key drivers (Curran, et al, 1994; Feghhi farahmand, 2005, 58).

For this reason, there is a need to re-track fundamental management systems. Such concepts as investment valuation, ethical trading, stakeholder consultation, corporate social responsibility, value investment, preoccupy institutional investor communities.

In any case, the level of uncertainty is continuing to increase even as consumer prosperity overlaps into the new century, reacting against the undoubted brilliance of the recent industrial era. However, the mainly qualitative evidence available to date suggests that SP within organizations is an activity of a minority (Bolton, et al, 2000, 88; Feghhi farahmand, 2002, 254). There may be a number of reasons for the lack of SP. Historically the typical speed of information flow has tended not to have pursued higher levels of education level or to take formal spontaneous behavior training. Hence there are two possible reasons why speed of information flow tend not to plan (Chell, 1991, et al, 167; Barkham, et al, 1996, 27) that they are emotionally unsuited to it. They think and act intuitively and they are simply unaware of the various tools which would enable them to plan systematically.

A further constraint, likely to restrict spontaneous behavior relationship by speed of information flow, is that they may not have sufficient financial information to prepare a formal plan. A lack of formal spontaneous behavior relationship planning may also relate to the fact that small organizations are just too busy surviving to take time out to plan ahead whilst others might argue the environment (Ledoux, 1993, 215; Ledoux, 1994, 15). A lack of formal spontaneous behavior relationship among organizations does not necessarily mean that organization is badly managed. It does, however, suggest that speed of information flow miss out on the opportunity to consider the overall direction of the spontaneous behavior and management decisions may be made on the basis of poor information (Curran, et al, 1994, 39; Feghhi farahmand, 2009, 102; Stutely, 2002, 43; Watts & et al, 2003, p 197).

The characteristics of the organization and speed of information flow and also organizations strategies hereafter termed spontaneous behavior relationship, influencing facilitator manager's behavior which might be used to inform analysis of the determinants of spontaneous behavior relationship in organizations. Organization characteristics were controlled out of analysis in order to focus our attention on the speed of information flow and spontaneous behavior relationship variables.

3. Speed of Information Flow

Organizational relationship management systems were both outcome focused and financially focused and were neither multidimensional nor strategic. The organizational relationship management became broader and included measures of innovation and service receiver satisfaction.

The most essential successful originated tools of organizations are:

- The spontaneous behavior relationship process management model;
- The spontaneous behavior relationship process auditing and assessment procedure of process successful;
- The spontaneous behavior relationship project management model;
- The spontaneous behavior relationship benchmarking procedure;

The nature of the speed of information flow is seen as critical in other aspects (Nayak et al, 1994, 425; Fisher, 2002, 89) of the activities of organizations. A selection of the speed of information flow' characteristics is the potential to

influence an owner manager's propensity to undertake organizational relationship management. Predictions of the direction in which the variables (Feghhi Farahmand, 2002, 345; Smith, 1967, 145) will operate are inevitably problematic as there is little prior work on the determinants of organizational relationship management upon which we can draw (Smith, 1967, 25; Curran, et al, 1994; Feghhi farahmand, 2005, 37; Kuratko & et al, 2004, 64):

- I. Spontaneous behavior relationship ability: This variable has been identified as important in a number of studies.
- II. Spontaneous behavior relationship experience: It may be strongly linked to ability and it could be argued that it might work in two ways. A long number of years running an organization as an speed of information flow might increase a propensity to plan future directions for the spontaneous behavior or indeed, once the initial phases had passed and funding secured planning might well be less of a priority.
- III. Spontaneous behavior relationship education level: In the context of organizational relationship management, this variable might seem reasonable to hypothesis that the more highly educated speed of information flow will tend to be more aware of the desirability of organizational relationship management and thus, organization run by the better educated speed of information flow might be more likely to have spontaneous behavior plans.
- IV. Spontaneous behavior relationship innovation: A distinction here may be drawn between those for whom the current organization is their first and serial founders.
- V. Spontaneous behavior relationship organizing: Organization founders are drawn either from operatives or from those with previous managerial experience.
- VI. Spontaneous behavior relationship strategy: Here it might be argued that speed of information flow moving into a new sector might be encouraged to plan rather more than those whose businesses were in sectors in which they had considerable prior experience.
- VII. Spontaneous behavior relationship potential: This was introduced into the analysis as it might be expected that local speed of information flow, who grew up in the geographical area under study, will tend to be introspective and less receptive to contemporary management practice.

The relationships between organizations and their localities have become an important research area and organization with links with local spontaneous behavior institutions might be more likely to spontaneous behavior plan. The argument here would be that mixing with local spontaneous behavior leaders would increase awareness of the value of organizational relationship management. Conversely, mixing with other speed of information flow of small organization might re-enforce towards the idea of organizational relationship management, especially where organizational relationship management was not seen as a key element of spontaneous behavior activity.

4. Spontaneous Behavior Relationship Management

Spontaneous behavior relationship management system is a technology-based organization management tool for developing and leveraging organizational customers' knowledge to maintain, and strengthen profitable relationships with service receivers. Thus, a spontaneous behavior relationship management system is an essential part of a global spontaneous behavior relationship management strategy which emphasis creation of satisfaction through the development of appropriate relationship with key service receivers segments. The underlying premise of spontaneous behavior relationship management is that organizational relationship creates organizational customers knowledge in order to:

- I. Spontaneous behavior relationship effectively segment organizational customers,

- II. Spontaneous behavior relationship develops and maintains long-term relationships with profitable organizational customers,
- III. Spontaneous behavior relationship determine how to handle unprofitable organizational customers.

Through the creation and better utilization of service receiver knowledge, the service receiver relationship should improve. Successful implementation of spontaneous behavior relationship management program depends upon four critical factors:

- I. Spontaneous behavior relationship management readiness assessment,
- II. Spontaneous behavior relationship management change management,
- III. Spontaneous behavior relationship management project management,
- IV. Spontaneous behavior relationship management employee engagement.

The capturing the wrong organizational customers information, unclear goals, inappropriate selection and use of technology, inability to integrate people and processes and use of misleading metrics or improper measurement approaches are the major barriers in implementing and managing organizational customers projects. The seven deadly sins for unsatisfactory spontaneous behavior relationship management outcome are:

- Viewing the spontaneous behavior relationship management initiative as a technology initiative;
- Lack of organizational customers vision;
- Insufficient appreciation of organizational customers' lifetime satisfies;
- Inadequate support from top management;
- Underestimating the importance of change management;
- Failing to re-engineer organization processes;

The spontaneous behavior relationship management refers to the internal systematic approach systematically of the organization management and leadership to strive for organization successful excellence. The successful spontaneous behavior relationship management referring to all those measures through which one creates and strengthens confidence and trust in outsiders, especially service receivers, towards the organization abilities and service. When the comprehensiveness of the spontaneous behavior relationship management approach is being emphasized one also can use the concept spontaneous behavior relationship management instead of spontaneous behavior plan. In practice, however, the both mean the same.

The aim of spontaneous behavior relationship management approach is to strive for the organization strategic and operational goals. Spontaneous behavior relationship management is based on a special expertise for enhancing effectiveness and efficiency of organization management and leadership. Thus genuine realization of the spontaneous behavior relationship management practices takes place in real organization activities both in the organization strategic leadership as well as in the operational realization of the organization services and targets.

The broad challenge for spontaneous behavior relationship management is to enhance positive substance of organization brand through various means that are consistent both with respect to one another and aligned with the organization strategic course.

As a whole the main principles in organizations approach include the following:

- Focus on supporting the spontaneous behavior relationship management strategic goals of the organization;

- Consistency of different spontaneous behavior relationship measures in order to strengthen one another;
- Alignment of the whole strategically and operationally for centering on the key issues;
- Comprehensiveness and a scope which covers the entire corporation;
- Integrating spontaneous behavior relationship management measures with organization processes.

Systematic approach instead of building separate systems such as quality systems spontaneous behavior relationship management approach is well harmonized with the organization strategies. On that basis also the quality policy was defined. General intention and direction towards spontaneous behavior relationship management is considered by the spontaneous behavior policy statements:

- Always act so that the organizational customers what he or she needs;
- Improve activities and their results continually so that they will be better and more effective and efficient of spontaneous behavior relationship management.

The goal of spontaneous behavior relationship management, i.e. organization excellence, is reached through innovative management and leadership practices.

In order to realize spontaneous behavior relationship management objectives in all parts of the organization and at all levels of organization and management, an organization-wide management structure, a leadership infrastructure framework has been defined. The framework model was originally created at organizations. This model covers all organization functions in a natural and flexible manner and covers the following four levels of the organization:

- I. The organization level: where the general principles, the common insight, goals, shared tools, and practices concerning spontaneous behavior relationship management are created, including how these principles are to be applied in practice on the basis of the organization requirements.
- II. The strategic areas and unit's level: where decisions are made by the general manager of the organization unit and the other top organization leaders, and measures undertaken concerning the entire particular organization and especially the future competitiveness of the organization and management of the whole organization system are addressed. The organization system is composed of the interrelated operational organization processes. Very often in corporations there are different organization areas that may be at different development stages. All these need different strategic spontaneous behavior relationship management approaches but they may operate within one corporate culture.
- III. The operational individual organization processes level: where decisions and measures concerning daily management are made and undertaken, and services are realized in real time for organizational customers needs.
- IV. The human and team's level: where the personal contribution of each member of the organization personnel including the top management is provided in natural working environments.

5. Results

Speed of information flow ranged in ability from low to high. Clearly, within this group, there is a sub set of growth oriented speed of information flow whose propensity to undertake organizational relationship management might be contrasted with those who were content with their current level of spontaneous behavior. The latter may well belong to that group of speed of information flow often characterized as running lifestyle organization. From this overview of the selected speed of information flow' characteristics and the strategies of the sampled organization, it is now possible to

explore the extent to which these differing characteristics and strategies influence whether or not an organization engages in organizational relationship management.

The main focus is on the role of speed of information flow characteristics in influencing the propensity for organizational relationship management. The interdisciplinary conceptual model will provide guidance to speed of information flow in developing contextually relevant method measures. The model provides speed of information flow with specific benefits such as:

- Measures to spontaneous behavior relationship management with strategically aligned framework for clearer logic behind spontaneous behavior relationship management actions.
- Successful measure portfolio that discriminates between spontaneous behavior relationship management efficiency and effectiveness successful measures in order to avoid suboptimal successful.
- Set of spontaneous behavior relationship management guidelines to ensure method synergies are achieved in the targeting of high and low organizational customers lifetime satisfy segments with matching method costs and method response to organizational customers satisfy.

6. Conclusion

Many of organizations have sustained their spontaneous behavior relationship management systems focus over time, although these investments may or may not be considered part of a long-term spontaneous behavior relationship management strategy. The scope, size, complexity and duration of the spontaneous behavior relationship management projects seem to vary quite significantly across organizations. Poor planning, lack of clear objectives and not recognizing the need for organization change are the key reasons for spontaneous behavior relationship failures.

The most recent spontaneous behavior relationship management programs, for example some have clearly benefited from previous spontaneous behavior relationship management systems experience of suppliers, including considerably reduced implementation times and lower risk levels for comparable size programs. All these organizations had very different levels of success. Their success was determined mainly by the relationship between the complexity of the system and the speed and phasing of its development and roll out. A spontaneous behavior relationship management system is not just service receiver interface software. Organizations believe that successful measurement frameworks should be multidimensional. Unfortunately, the early attempts at successful measurement frameworks were too financially oriented and did not provide strategic vision.

Speed of information flow have too many successful measures, and a simplified set with fewer yet more important metrics would lead to superior successful. Successful speed of information flow are hindered by too many low-level measures. Ideal successful speed of information flow must include measures which are strategically relevant as well as measures which address both efficiency and effectiveness of spontaneous behavior relationship management. For speed of information flow, the area of organizational relationship method successful measurement is an area that represents a significant opportunity for spontaneous behavior relationship management investment and spontaneous behavior plan management attention. In order to understand whether the speed of information flow is performing or not, we need to ensure that the speed of information flow is appropriate for each spontaneous behavior strategy. In response to this research gap, this paper investigates whether speed of information flow should differ according to spontaneous behavior strategy. Speed of information flow were asked whether or not they had a formal organizational relationship management for their organization and the period of time to which it applied.

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